

RENEWABLE ENERGY EFFICIENCY CALCULATION

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Abstract. A majority of the communities around the world rely heavily on oil, natural gas and coal for their energy needs. These fuels draw on lots of resources that will eventually diminish, which in turn makes them too expensive or too environmentally damaging to recover. This review article discusses the advantages and disadvantages of renewable energies; therefore based on the benefits of these energy resources, the use of renewable energies, instead of, fossil fuels will be a good solution for the control of the environmental, social and economical problems of our communities.

Keywords: Renewable Energy, Environment, Sustainability, Green Energy

1. Background

Based on statistical data from 2011 by the US Department of Energy Information, primary consumption of energy by source and sectors were [1]:

Table1. Energy sources for different sectors of the society in the US

Sources of Energy	% Use	Consumption by Sectors	%Use
Petroleum	36%	Commercial	40%
Natural Gas	26%	Transportation	28%
Coal	20%	Industrial	21%
Renewable Energy	9%	Residential	11%
Nuclear Electric Power	8%		

The above data shows almost 90% of sources of energy in the US were non-renewable; therefore it would be beneficial to employ renewable energy resources (wind, solar, geothermal, wave and biomass energy) because of their availability and cleanliness.

Renewable energy is derived from natural processes that are replenished constantly. In its various forms, it derives directly from the sun, wind, rain, tides of ocean, biomass and geothermal resources from heat generated deep within the earth. In 2008, about 19% of global final energy consumption came from renewable, with 13% coming from traditional biomass, and 3.2% from hydroelectricity. The share of renewable in electricity generation is around 18%, with 15% of global electricity coming from hydroelectricity and 3% from new renewable. Renewable energy replaces conventional fuels in four distinct areas: power generation, hot water, transport fuels and rural (off-grid) energy services [2]

The selection of energy has global implications that affect greenhouse gas emissions, water resource distribution, mineral consumption, and equipment manufacturing and transportation. The school of thought is that renewable energy technologies are more sustainable than many current sources of energy. There is a need for verification of the sustainability of renewable energy, which can easily be done by resource-use optimization, techno-economic feasibility and cost analysis, life cycle assessment, environmental externalities analysis, cost benefits analysis, manufacturing cost analysis, research and development targets and barrier identification and water requirements and distribution analysis. [3]

In general renewable energies are not adaptable to every single community because of two main factors, the distribution of the natural resources that has dependency on the geographical locations and energy-use with its dependency on the culture of individual community. The other limitations are growth rate and infrastructure.

Application of any renewable energy requires a sustainability analysis, which has dependency on three main components: environmental effects, externalities costs, and economics and financing. Each one of these variables has a major impact on the application of renewable energies; therefore before committing communities to different sorts of renewable energies, a thorough research must be done in order to have an assurance that no social, environmental or economical problems arise or are compromised because of them. [3]

2. Renewable Energies

This paper reviews advantages and disadvantages of few common renewable energies: hydropower, solar power, wind power, geothermal power and biomass. Hopefully after studying this review article, the public has a better understanding about renewable energies.

2.1 Hydropower

Hydropower is a clean and renewable energy source. Considering the economic, technical and environmental benefits of hydropower, most countries give priority to its development. For example, China has the richest hydro resources on the planet with a total theoretical hydropower potential of 694GW. Developing hydropower is of great importance to alleviate the energy crisis and environmental pollution resulting from the rapid economic growth of China and other countries in the 21st century. [4]

Hydropower is generated using the mechanical energy of flowing water by forcing it through piping called a penstock, which then turns a generator in order to produce electricity. Water power also consists of wave and tidal energy, which are both in the infant stage of research, as scientists try to discover how to harness the energy produced from movement of the ocean. [5]

Hydropower has several advantages over most other sources generating electrical power. These include a high level of reliability, proven technology, high efficiency, very low operating and maintenance costs, and the ability to easily adjust to load changes. Generally many hydropower plants are located in conjunction with reservoirs, which provide water, flood control, and recreation benefits for the community. In addition, hydropower does not produce waste products that cause acid rain, and greenhouse gases.

Disadvantages of hydropower include high initial costs of facilities; dependence on precipitation (no control over amount of water available); changes in stream regimens (can affect fish, plants, and wildlife by changing stream levels, flow patterns, and temperature); inundation of land and wildlife habitat (creation of reservoir); and displacement of people living in the reservoir area. [6]

2.2 Solar Power

Solar power is the most abundant renewable resource on our planet. In spite of this abundance, only 0.04% of the basic power used by humans comes directly from solar sources because using a photovoltaic (PV) panel costs more than burning fossil fuels. Organic materials have recently been intensively studied for PV applications, not because of harvesting the sun's power more efficiently, but because power generation from organic photovoltaic (OPV) materials will cost considerably less than other PV technologies. [7]

Concentrating solar power uses the heat from the sun to produce steam, which in turn powers a generator that creates electricity. This also has low operating costs and high efficiency, and can produce a reliable supply of energy by utilizing thermal storage. [8]

The cost of new photovoltaic power is dropping rapidly, and if the photovoltaic industry continues to grow and improve technologically, by 2020 the cost will be comparable to the cost of conventional power, as will the cost of solar thermal power. [9-10]

Solar energy is a true renewable resource. Most of planet earth has the ability to collect some amount of solar power. Solar energy is non-polluting, does not create greenhouse gases, such as oil based energy does, nor does it create waste that must be stored, such as nuclear energy. It is also far quieter to create and harness, drastically reducing the noise pollution required converting energy to a useful form. Residential size solar energy systems also have very little impact on the surrounding environment, in contrast with other renewable energy sources such as wind and hydro electric power. Solar panels have no moving parts and require very little maintenance beyond regular cleaning. Without moving parts to break and replace, after the initial costs of installing the panels, maintenance and repair costs are very reasonable. It should also be noted that photovoltaic solar panels are the only source considered with the potential to satisfy existing demand. [11-12]

The main problem of using solar energy is the cost involved. Despite advances in technology, solar panels remain almost prohibitively expensive. Even when the cost of the panels is ignored, the system required to store the energy for use can also be quite costly. Although some solar energy can be collected during even the cloudiest of days, efficient solar energy collection is dependent on sunshine. Even a few cloudy days can have a large effect on an energy system, particularly once the fact that solar energy cannot be collected at night is taken into account. [13]

Finally on the basis of the science, it is wrong to support the use of all biomass resources, with any conversion technology and for any application. It would also be unreasonable to oppose all biomass on the basis that some of the biomass resources, conversion or applications are not sustainable or beneficial! Therefore the best solution is to educate our communities to choose the best resources for generation of biomass energy!

3. Results

It is very clear scientists are faced with a very hard job to convince public to divert their attentions toward renewable energies and forget about the convenience of working and dealing with fossil fuels on a daily basis! Having said that I know for fact all it takes to make public aware of the problems associated with fossil fuels is to present them with some statistical data about health issues as well as

environmental catastrophe from some of the major big cities around the world! We should also create an environment in which usage of renewable energies becomes rewarding (i.e., tax incentive) in order to encourage people to use them.

One of the best communities within the U.S. that promotes renewable energies as well as sustainable living is the City of Portland in Oregon! Portland could and should be used as a role model within the field of sustainability everywhere; because of its promotion of renewable energies for the new and existing communities, public transportation, and the famous three Rs (Recycle, Reuse and Reduce)!

Luckily based on the performance of the available renewable energy sources and findings of the U.S. Energy Information Administration (Fig. 1-3), public has realized the health impacts of fossil fuels as well as its impact on the environment; therefore they have slowly turned toward renewable energies [22]. Hopefully within the next decade, the jump in the consumption of the renewable energies will be far greater than few percent!

Fig. 1. U.S. Energy consumption and Renewable Energy consumption 2006-2010 [22].

Fig. 2. Renewable Energy as share of total primary consumption in 2010 [22].

4. Conclusion

It is necessary that we take precautions when distributing and consuming the earth's resources. The current use of natural gas and fossil fuels combined with increasing global population has caused the earth's resources to be abused and depleted. The effects on the environment are exhausting and threatening to the sustainability of the earth. The way we have been consuming fossil fuels is very scary; and the scarier point is the fact that during last couple of decades the consumption of fossil fuels has gone up. The oil reserves across the world are diminishing, and energy production currently depends too highly on oil and fuels, which contribute to the emission of greenhouse gases. Release of pollutants into the atmosphere has dire consequences, including global warming; therefore it is necessary to protect planet earth by incorporating renewable, eco-friendly energy sources in our daily lives!

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